

Pattern of Early Childhood Development in Screen Used Children of Bangladesh. A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract

Objectives: To evaluate the pattern of early childhood development in screen used children of Bangladesh.

Methods: This cross sectional type of study was conducted at Department of Paediatric Neurology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) from June 2023 to November 2023. Children aged 1-5 years who use mobile phone, more than 1 hour in a day were selected and enrolled in this study. Neurodevelopmental assessment was done by Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA) and General Developmental Assessment (GDA).

Results: Total 110 children were included. Among them about three-fourth 81 (73.6%) of patients were male and 29 (26.3%) were female and male female ratio was 2.7:1. More than half (58.1%) children passed 3-5 hours by using mobile screen. More than three-fourth 90 (81.8%) children used screen during eating followed by before sleeping (37.2 %).

About half 51(46.4%) of patients had abnormal speech development followed by Social problem 34(30.9%), cognitive delay 12(10.9%) and motor delay 6(5.4%). Regarding abnormal speech development, study showed more than one- third of children (39.2%) presented with speech regression, followed by self talking behaviour 37.2%, speech delay 13.7% and no speech 9.8%. Nearly half of the child had sleep disturbance (44.5%).

Conclusion: This study concludes that more than half of the children passed 3-5 hours by using mobile screen. More than three-fourth children used screen during eating and before sleeping. Commonly found early childhood developmental disorders were abnormal speech development, social problem and cognitive delay.

Introduction

Nowadays, digital technologies have progressively become an integral part of the life of children for communication as well as learning and playing [1]. Computer, television, iPad, or mobile device are the time consuming electronic media [2] Screens have an omnipresent presence in children's day-to-day lives, are easy to use and serve as a popular platform for

activity and entertainment [3]. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), screen time is not allowed for children below two years of age, and screen time should be no longer than one hour per day for children aged two to four years [4].

Preschool children (3–4 years) experience rapid growth and development of cognitive, language and executive functioning domains. Excessive screen time is related

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Keywords:

Early childhood development, Screen used children.

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to poor early motor and cognitive development outcomes in children [6,7]. Moreover there is an increased risk of obesity, attention problems and hyperactivity, sleep problems, unsatisfactory academic performance and unhappiness [7,8]. Longer screen time for children may reduce involvement in interactive activities with other children or adults and may lead to fewer learning scopes [9,10]. So global increases in screen time for children are of major concern given child development may have long-term consequences over the life course including on adult productivity [11]. So, it is our interest to evaluate the pattern of early childhood development in screen used children of Bangladesh.

Materials and Methods

This cross sectional type of study was conducted at Department of Paediatric Neurology, Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU) from June 2023 to November 2023. Children aged 1-5 year who use mobile phone, more than 1 hour in a day were selected and enrolled in this study. Children with known cerebral palsy, intellectual disability, Down syndrome, Autism were excluded from this study. The duration of the study was 6 months. Total 110 children were included of both sexes. Then children were assessed thoroughly by taking detailed history and physical examination. Neurodevelopmental assessment was done by Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA) and General Developmental Assessment (GDA). Data was collected in pre-designed structured questionnaire. Institutional review board approved this study. In addition, an informed written consent was taken from the parents or the legal guardians of the studied subjects. Data were presented in tabulated form. Data were analyzed using computer based program Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) for Windows version 23.

Operational definition

Rapid Neurodevelopmental Assessment (RNDA) Scale is an assessment tool designed to ascertain functional status in nine domains: primitive reflexes, gross and fine motor development, vision, hearing, speech, cognition, behavior and seizures [12].

General Developmental Assessment (GDA) refers to the systematic assessment and integration of a person’s developmental characteristics [13].

Table 1: Distribution of Study Population According to Baseline Characteristics of the Patients (N=110)

Baseline characteristics of patients	Number of patients (n=110)	Percentage (%)
Age (years)		
1-2	24	21.8
2-3	46	41.8
3-5	40	36.5

Sex		
Male	81	73.6
Female	29	26.3
Residence		
Rural	36	32.7
Urban	74	67.3
Social Class		
Lower	17	15.4
Middle	58	52.7
Higher	35	31.8

Table 1 shows the distribution of study population according to particulars of patients. It was observed that nearly half (41.8%) of patients belonged to age 2-3 years. Almost three fourth (73%) of patients were male and 29(26.3%) were female. Male with female ratio was (2.7:1).

Table 2: Distribution of Study Population According to Duration of Screen Use (N=110)

Duration of time used before screen by children (hour)	Number of patients (110)	Percentage (%)
1-2	20	18.1
3-5	64	58.1
>5	26	23.6

Table 2 shows that more than half (58.1%) children pass 3-5 hours before screen.

Table 3: Distribution of Study Population According to Pattern of Screen Use (n=110)

Pattern of use of screen	Number of patients (110)	Percentage (%)
During eating	90	81.8
Before sleeping	41	37.2
For Teaching	10	9.0
For music/cartoon	23	20.9
For playing mobile game	30	27.2
As pacifier	12	10.9

Table 3 shows that more than two- third 90 (81.8%) children used screen during eating and during sleeping, playing games, for music/cartoon, as pacifier, for teaching 37.2 %, 27.2%,20.9%,10.9%,9%respectively.

Table 4: Distribution of Study Population According to Development History (N=110)

Development history	Number of patients (n)	Percentage (%)
Abnormal Speech development		
Present	51	46.4
Absent	59	53.6
Cognitive delay		

Present	12	10.9
Absent	98	89.1
Motor delay		
Present	6	5.4
Absent	104	94.6
Vision Problem		
Present	2	1.8
Absent	108	98.2
Hearing Problem		
Present	12	9
Absent	98	81
Social/Behavioral problem		
Present	34	30.9
Absent	76	69.1

Table 4 shows that about half (46.4%) of patients had abnormal speech development followed by Social/behavioral problem 34 (30.9%), cognitive delay 12 (10.9%) and motor delay 6 (5.4%).

Table 5: Distribution of Study Population According to Pattern of Abnormal Speech Development

Pattern of Speech development	Number of patients (51)	Percentage (%)
No Speech	5	9.8
Normal speech but delay	7	13.7
Self-talking behavior	19	37.2
Speech regression	20	39.2

Table 5 shows More than one-third of children presented with speech regression (39.2%), Self talking behavior, speech delay, no speech development was present in 37.2%, 13.7%, and 9.8% respectively.

Table 6: Distribution of Study Population by Associated Co-Occurring Condition (n=110)

Associated co-occurring condition	Number of patients (110)	Percentage (%)
Sleep disturbance		
Present	49	44.6
Absent	61	55.4
Gratification syndrome		
Present	6	5.4
Absent	104	94.6
Aggressive behavior		
Present	7	6.3
Absent	103	93.7
GIT abnormality		
Present	10	9
Absent	110	91

Table 6 shows that nearly half of the child had sleep disturbance (44.5%). GIT abnormality, aggressive behavior and gratification syndrome was present in 9%, 6.3% and 5.4% respectively.

Discussion

Children in preschool age (3–4 years) experience rapid growth and development of cognitive, language and executive functioning domains and other skills such as working memory and self- control during this time period. However, children’s communicative and cognitive development is affected by their environment and experiences. In one study it is suggested that, excessive screen time is either associated negatively with or provides no benefits for cognitive development [14]. In other study it also found that many preschoolers cross the limit by national and international screen time recommendations (i.e., < 1 h/day) [15]. Increased screen time in this age group is thought to be replacing normal daily activities of children that are beneficial for their language and cognitive development [16].

In this study, it was observed that nearly half (41.8%) of patients belonged to age 2-3 years. One study in North America had similarity with our study where it is estimated that about 50% of children two years of age spend more than one hour/day watching television which also match with our finding [17]. Similarly a study in Asia found that the prevalence of TV exposure greater than one hour/day was 76.7% among two year old children, and in Thailand 90% of two year of children had greater than one hour per day of screen time exposure [18,19]. Almost three fourth (73%) of patients were male and 29(26.3%) were female in our study. A study in Thailand indicated 60% of boys and 55% of girls of preschool children (4–5 years) had high screen time that is male passed more time than female before screen [20]. In our finding, more than three fourth (74%) of patients came from urban area and 36(32.7%) from rural area. Almost half (52.7%) of patients belonged to middle class family, 17(15.4%) lower and 35(31.8%) from higher class. It is found that, children facing socio-economic vulnerability including low family income spent more time in screen-based activities [21]. Määtä S et al. stated that parents from lower socioeconomic status, child care is difficult to afford and they often have other competing demands (e.g., work, other caregiving responsibilities) while taking care of younger children [22]. More than two-third (81.8%) children used screen during eating and during sleeping, playing games, for music/cartoon, as pacifier, for teaching 37.2 %, 27.2 %, 20.9 %, 10.9%, 9% respectively. Alroqi H et al. also found that children spent the majority of screen time watching child-directed non-educational content on all screens [23]. In one study, this type of finding may be the results of parents using screens to entertain or occupy children

while they complete other tasks [24]. Our study found about half (46.4%) of patients had speech delay followed by Social/Behavioral problem 34 (30.9%), cognitive delay 12(10.9%) and motor delay 6 (5.4%). A study performed in Boston college also found that high levels of screen time are of concern for developmental health because it tends to displace free play-based and leisure activities that enhance cognitive and social-emotional skills [25]. Regarding speech abnormalities, our study showed more than one-third of children presented with speech regression (39.2%), abnormal self-talking behavior, speech delay, no speech development was present in 37.2%, 13.7%, and 9.8% respectively. Al Hosani SS et al. found that, 90.3% of those who have speech and language development delay use electronic devices [26]. In our study, nearly half of the child had sleep disturbance (44.5%). GIT abnormality, aggressive behavior and gratification syndrome was present in 9%, 6.3% and 5.4% respectively. In one study performed in USA stated that excessive use of technology can lead to addiction, poor sleep quality, and obesity in children [27].

Conclusion

This study finds that children's exposure to digital screens continues to increase alarmingly and increased duration of screen exposure is related to poorer child's language development as well as social and cognitive development. Moreover, excessive screen use is associated with much co-occurring condition like sleep disturbance, behavioral problems, GIT problems etc.

Limitations and Recommendation

Limitation of this study is a cross sectional and single centred study.

Further intervention should be done to reduce child's screen exposure and to promote normal child development.

Conflict of Interest

There was no conflict of interest.

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Author Contributions

Conceive and study design and data analysis: Prof. Dr. Gopen Kumar Kundu.

Clinical Help: Dr Umme Habiba, Dr Sk. Serjina Anwar, Sharmina Afrin

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